

Short name	MRV Readiness	Long name	MRV Readiness
Geographical scope	All regions		
Description of how this issue tends to manifest (include footnotes for key references)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - MRV is an important element of carbon markets to ensure transparency and accuracy in tracking emissions reductions. - MRV typically involves measuring and verifying emissions reductions through various methods, such as on-site inspections, data analysis, and remote sensing. - Third-party verifiers are often used to ensure impartiality and accuracy in the MRV process. - MRV requirements may differ depending on the type of carbon market and the specific project or program involved. - Compliance with MRV requirements is necessary to generate carbon credits and participate in carbon markets, which can provide financial incentives for emissions reductions. <p>Project developers must provide detailed monitoring, reporting, and verification of their emissions reductions or removals, which are then reviewed by independent auditors or verifiers to ensure compliance with established standards and methodologies.</p>		
Key examples where this issue manifests (also based on stakeholder inputs)	<p>Expert judgement based on the following factors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Known presence of geological survey companies - Known previous participation of key actors in carbon markets - Existence of (plans for) CCS activities - Oil/gas industry activity - Existence of a carbon tax or other policy requiring monitoring of CO₂-flows 		
Other issues this affects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CRCF - EU CCS Directive - MRV methodologies - CCS+ initiative - Liability (in hubs) - Leakage penalties 		
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Poralla, M.; Honegger, M.; Gameros, C. et al. (2022): Tracking greenhouse gas removals: baseline and monitoring methodologies, additionality testing, and accounting, NET-Rapido Consortium and Perspectives Climate Research, London, UK and Freiburg i.B., Germany - Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) (2019): 2019 Refinement to the 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National GHG Inventories - Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) (2006): 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories 		